

**The Effect of Game Format and Team and Pitch Size on the
Technical Actions and Physical Load of Youth Footballers in
Small Sided Games**

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ABSTRACT

Rationale: The present study examines the effects that different pitch size and game formats have on the technical actions and physical load of adolescent footballers of differing maturity levels. **Methodology:** The research consisted of 48 adolescent footballers (13.47 ± 0.85 years old) from two separate Club Academy Scotland youth academies. Over 3 weeks the adolescent footballers performed Small Sided Games in 4v4, 5v5 and 6v6 pitch size and mixed, matched, and mismatched game formats. They were categorised in to 'Less Mature' and 'More Mature' groups based upon their APHV. Their Maturity offset was calculated using the Fransen Equation. **Results:** It was found that both pitch size and game formats do have an effect on the two different maturity groups within key physical & technical metrics needed for successful performance in football. The results showed that increases in team and pitch size appeared to provide the opportunity for MM to use their increased physical capabilities to perform greater physical and technical actions than LM. Game formats can have varying effects on the two differing maturity groups, such as 'Mismatched' and 'Mixed' games allowing the MM to perform a greater number of technical actions than LM, while 'Matched' games saw LM perform a greater number of physical actions than MM. However, it must be noted that the effects of game formats had on technical and physical demands were lessened by the reduction of relative pitch size. **Conclusion:** Team & Relative Pitch Size and Game Format should be carefully considered by youth football coaches when designing practices, when looking to -
=develop certain characteristics within a group of adolescent footballers of differing maturity levels. If looking to widely develop a mixed maturity group, then it can be recommended to use a smaller Team & Relative Pitch Size.

1.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Introduction

There have been a number of investigations into Bio Banding (BB), Small Sided Games (SSG) and their effects on footballers technically (Towlson et al, 2021), physically (Barrett et al, 2022) However, no investigation has examined the combined effects. That is why it was deemed important to perform the current project to examine how relative pitch size and game format can impact perceived exertion, physical load, and technical performance in adolescent footballers of differing levels of maturity during SSG.

1.2 Bio Banding

BB is the concept of grouping young athletes, in this studies case; young footballers, based on their level of maturation instead of the more common way of using their chronological age (Stanila et al, 2020). This concept dates back over 100 years with Roch (1908) proposing the use of the term anatomical age, and that it may be beneficial in some situations during schooling and sports. It has been shown by Cummings et al (2017) that early maturing adolescents experience a more intense growth spurt, resulting in rapid pubertal gains in height, weight, and lean muscle mass. Cummings et al (2017) continues to state that this intense maturation allows the early maturing adolescents to benefit from potential sporting advantages such as greater size, strength, speed and power, especially in the ages between 11 – 14. The use of BB within football was to attempt to reduce these physical differences that create biases within team and academy selections. Unnithan et al (2012) stated that a large percentage of perceived talent indicators related to footballers' capabilities, such as height, weight, body size, power. Reeves et al (2018) found within their research that these physical increases were creating biases towards early maturing footballers within team selection and talent identification situations,

due to football practitioners more likely to favour this group of players. Due to this, earlier maturing footballers have been found to benefit from higher standards of coaching and increased levels of competition than late maturing footballers (Reeves et al, 2018). While Stanila et al (2020) found that the differing physical capabilities were discouraging late maturing footballers from continuing to participate, not only due to selection issues but also performance issues from being unable to compete against stronger, faster and more powerful opponents. In recent years the focus upon BB in sports research has grown. One possible reason for this could be associated with the exclusive use of grouping by chronological age in youth sports. Reeves et al (2018) performed a 7-week investigation into the use of BB within a professional youth academy. During Reeves et al's (2018) study they found the use of chronological age to be problematic. The authors found that it was simply used due to convenience and simplicity, while not accounting for the individual differences in maturity and varying levels of physical prowess. Further evidence supporting that chronological age may not be the greatest method of grouping youth footballers can be found in the investigation performed by Lovell et al (2019). In Lovell et al's (2019) research they found that the effects of maturation can influence a footballer's physical capability's during games of football, with an example being match running performance. More mature footballers were found to cover greater distance at greater speed than less mature footballers. Furthermore, Cumming et al (2017) suggested that maturation could also provide benefits of strength, sport competence and self-esteem. The findings of Unnithan's (2012) study investigating talent identification in football can provide evidence of the issues surrounding the greater physical capabilities of early maturing youth footballers. The findings showed that physical performance in youth footballers is only an indication of their current performance level and should not be used to indicate future performance levels (Unnithan, 2012). Further impact of BB can be clearly viewed in literature investigating BB within youth football performed by Towlson et al (2021).

Within the study Towlson et al (2021) investigated the effect that BB had on physical and psychological indicators of talent identification in academy footballers. The authors found that coaches and scouts, while performing talent identification of youth footballers, leaned heavily upon physical characteristics that are attributed to maturation such as stature, speed, power. Bradley et al's (2022) findings appear to suggest the same, with the consequences being that late-maturing youth footballers are overlooked, excluded, and subsequently denied further developmental activities. Furthermore, Towlson et al (2021) highlighted further potential issues with using chronological age within a talent identification setting, due to maturity levels having been shown to have an influence on the performance of physical, tactical, and technical attributes of adolescent footballers. As well as reducing the effects of the use of chronological age, BB can have a positive impact on footballer development. Romann et al (2020) found its use within training games resulted in the physical demands on footballers being reduced, thus resulting in the games becoming more technically and tactically challenging for the young footballers. However, Romann et al's (2020) findings appeared to not fully agree with past research from Abbott et al (2019). With their research having found that while BB did increase the technical demand on young footballers, it did so without reducing the physical demands (Abbott et al, 2019). While Moran et al (2021) suggested the benefits that BB can reduce the likelihood of young footballers dropping out of the sport due to it appearing to reduce the risk of injury. These benefits can all be related to Macmaster et al (2021) who noted that the use of BB creates a homogenous group of young footballers who have a similar maturity status and hold similar physical qualities.

1.3 Small Sided Games

SSG's are one of the most commonly used training drills within football, both in senior and youth football. Halouani et al (2014) believed their high usage is largely due to the coaches'

ability to adapt the SSG's to target differing tactical, technical or physical aims while allowing the players to perform in as close to game-like conditions as possible. Despite the wide-spread use of SSG's across both youth and senior football there remains unanswered questions about how best to implement them in order to maximise their impact when developing the aforementioned domains. One method being commonly used by practitioners, particularly in youth football is BB. BB is the practice of grouping youth athletes on the basis of attributes associated with growth and maturation instead of chronological age, as it is believed that it can have positive effects on footballers experiencing different stages of their growth and maturation development (Stanila et al, 2020). SSGs are an adapted format of football games played with less footballers within differing areas of pitch (Clemente et al, 2021). SSG's have become tools of great use to coaches due to them providing the same specific movement patterns and physiological demands as a full-sized game of football (Halouani et al, 2014). Bergkamp et al (2020) found that SSG's can be representative of full sided games apart from the number of aerial duels performed. While Fernandez-Espinola et al (2020) championed the use of SSG's within training sessions due to their ability to integrate physical, technical, and tactical behaviour stimuli in similar conditions to a real game. Although all SSG's are played with a reduced number of footballers and in an adapted, often smaller, size of pitch, the specifics of these changes can have an impact on the type of game that will occur and the effect that it will have upon the footballers participating in it. In order to analyse the technical outcomes of footballers during full sized football games and SSGs, there are certain technical outputs that are commonly collected. Kelly et al (2020) examined possession, pass completion and total touches to analyse youth academy footballers' technical ability within their study. While Lewis et al (2022) used ball releases, high speed ball releases and ball release index to analyse footballers within games, with their findings suggesting the speed of the technical actions is a key performance indicator during games of football. However, it must be noted that Lewis et

al's (2022) study was focused on adult footballers. Clemente et al (2021) found in their systematic review of 50 studies that manipulations and adaptations of SSG's can promote immediate effects on the footballer's behaviours, thus effecting their technical execution and physical outputs. The impact upon the tactical outputs can be viewed within Clemente et al's (2020) study, which found by reducing the size of the playing area there was an increase in penetrative attacking movements and also an increase in delaying defensive actions. When the size of the playing area was increased, the authors found that teams used more unity in both defence and attack while the overall variability of individual footballer movement was increased. The impact of SSG's on technical outputs can be viewed in the results of Clemente & Sarmiento's (2020) research, who found that the use of a 3v3 format as opposed to a 6v6 format saw increases in technical actions such as conquered balls, received balls, lost balls, attacking balls and shots. The study also presented evidence that there was a correlation between the number of sets performed and the number of technical actions carried out (Clemente & Sarmiento, 2020). Sarmiento et al (2018) found within their systematic review of SSG's in youth football that the bigger the pitch size used, the more accelerations, decelerations and total distance was performed by youth footballers during SSG's. Halouani et al's (2014) findings match those of Clemente et al (2021), however they also introduce the concept that the coach's behaviour can also have an effect on the footballer's output through the use or non-use of encouragement. Aguiar et al (2012) performed a review examining the effects of SSG's, in particular how adaptations to the format can affect the footballers, technically, tactically, and physically. They agreed with the findings above that the number of footballers, size of pitch, and coach's encouragement can affect the footballer's physical, technical, and tactical output, however they continued to add the rules of the game to also have an effect. The authors found that the use of fewer footballers increased the physical demands experienced by the footballers, increased the number of touches, and overall technical work of the footballers, and finally

resulted in the footballers giving higher ratings of perceived exertion (RPE). Aguiar et al (2012) continued to suggest that the use of more footballers saw a potential increase in overall distance covered and a greater number of overall sprints, however they did acknowledge that these findings were not as strong as the other findings shared, as the studies had used different methods to collect their data which made comparisons difficult. The authors also investigated the impact of changing the size of pitch, with larger pitches producing higher RPE from the footballers. Furthermore, smaller pitches were found to result in less overall distance covered, and while it did result in less time with the ball in play, it also resulted in the footballers performing more technical actions on the ball. When looking at the impact of the change of rules, Aguiar et al (2012) focused on the use or non-use of goalkeepers within the SSG's. They found there to be an increase in game intensity when a goalkeeper was used, which they attributed to the footballers having to perform more defensive actions. Finally, they found that the use of coach encouragement influenced the footballer's physiological response, more so than any other of the adaptations (i.e., change of footballer, change of size of pitch, change of rules). (Aguiar et al, 2012). The present study examines the effects that different pitch size and game formats have on the technical actions and physical load of adolescent footballers of differing maturity levels. There have been studies examining different aspects of SSG's and how they can impact the performance and development of youth footballers, none have looked at the effect of relative pitch size combined with BB and Non-BB formats to analyse the impact on a footballer's RPE and technical and physical performance. Towlson et al (2021) used differing BB and Non-BB SSG's formats to investigate their impact on youth footballers' physical outputs similar to this study, but they did not also consider the effects of this on the technical and RPE on the youth footballers. While Clemente et al (2021) investigated the effects of adapting SSG's format on youth footballers' technical performance, they did not also investigate the effect on the footballer's physical outputs and RPE. Additionally, there is a lack

of consensus around the best way to implement BB within youth football. Towlson et al (2020) discussed within their study the limitations of the use of both the Fransen equation and Khamis-Roche equation, in particular questioning their effectiveness when used in heterogeneous cohorts often found with football academies. Due to the outstanding questions in relation to the way SSG's are prescribed in youth football, there may be ways that coaches could use SSG's to maximise footballer development that are not currently understood.

1.4. Internal and External Load

To measure the physiological impact that training and games have on footballers, the practitioner should measure both the footballers internal and external loads. Sobolewski (2020) states that external loads are associated with physical work being done by the body in the form of movement such as total distance covered and accelerations, while internal loads are measures of a biochemical and the biomechanical stress on the system, with examples being heart rate and RPE. The authors continue that internal and external loads are often used to determine whether the training being prescribed to an athlete is enough to provide the appropriate stimulus to promote physiological adaptation. However, it is also used to determine whether the training load is too much for the athlete, which could result in fatigue or injury (Sobolewski, 2020). The most common methods used to quantify internal load are Global Positioning Systems (GPS), heart rate monitors and athletes reporting an RPE. RPE is believed to have benefits to its use as it accounts for the athletes own personal feelings, as well as taking in information from the sessions difficulty as a whole instead of simply the physical outputs recorded with GPS and heart rate monitors (Haddad et al, 2017). Haddad et al (2017) continued to explain how the RPE scores collected can be analysed using the single arbitrary unit method. The RPE scores are most commonly collected using a CR-10 BORG Scale, this uses numbers to score the RPE, with 1 being very easy and 10 being maximum (Haddad et al, 2017) (Borg, 1982). To allow these scores to be better analysed the single arbitrary unit method requires the collected RPE score to be multiplied by the volume (duration) of the training session ($AU = RPE \times \text{Session Duration}$) (Haddad et al, 2017). Rago et al (2019) found the use of RPE to be far cheaper and simpler than the use of GPS. While Haddad et al (2017) championed the use of RPE with youth footballers as they found its use to be efficient and consistent. However, they continued to question whether it would be suitable for younger adolescents as it did require the user to express their own personal feelings which they

conceded may affect the reliability if the younger adolescents are not aided with this aspect, as they believed it would take them longer to fully understand the question in order to answer correctly (Haddad et al, 2017). Regarding external loads Sobolewski (2020) states that the most commonly used methods in football research are speed zones, accelerations and total distance covered. Clubb et al (2022) agreed with these findings but also included number of efforts above absolute. Clubb et al (2022) continued within their research to highlight some things that may affect a footballers internal and external load. Salter's (2016) research had previously analysed this effect but also comparing it to the maturity levels of the footballers. The author found that there was no significant difference between the internal and external loads, when quantified by X and Y, respectively, of footballers at differing maturity levels. However, a more recent study performed by Towlson et al (2021) suggests that a footballers maturity level may have an effect on their internal and external load. Club et al (2022) continued within their study to state that changes within SSG's in football, such as the number of footballers participating, the size of the area used, the rules and coach encouragement all have an effect of an individual external and internal loads. Further research into the effects of SSG's on youth footballers RPE (Sanchez et al 2017) found an increase in RPE scores during games where 'floating' footballers were used compared to games when they were not used. Although there has been research into effects of pitch sizes and research into the effect of differing game formats, there has not previously been any research to examine the impact of relative pitch size and differencing game formats (BB, mixed and mis-matched) on adolescents internal and external loads.

1.5 Adolescent footballer Development

It has been well established through the literature produced on SSG's that the actions of the coach can have an effect on the outcomes of the footballers internal and external load (Aguiar et al, 2012). It has clearly been shown that the coaches' actions to change the size of pitch, the size of team or to provide encouragement or not influences the footballers external (Clemente et al, 202) and internal (Aguiar et al, 2012) loads. Another context in which the actions of the lead practitioner can affect the outcomes of the footballer is their individual development during adolescence. These effects can be related back to the findings of Vygotsky (1978) and his development of the concept, the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The ZPD is described as the distance between the actual development level of an adolescent as determined by their independent problem-solving and the level of their potential development as determined through their ability to problem solve while under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers (Vygotsky, 1978, P.86) (Garcia-Farina et al, 2021). Vygotsky's (1978) idea follows the thinking that what children are capable of within a group of peers being led by a more experienced individual is more illustrative of their mental development than independent work (Vinson & Parker, 2019). The findings of using this concept are that young people's development occurs more rapidly when they are working within their ZPD (Bowler et al, 2005). Thus, suggesting that that through the adaption of the set up and rules, a practitioner or coach can use the environment of the SSG's to create situations that may maximise the development of the young footballers. These findings mirror those that were found previously in the internal and external load studies, showing that any adaptations the coach makes to the SSG could affect the technical, tactical, and physiological outputs of young footballers. Further benefits of considering the ZPD during youth development is that it is believed it can accelerate footballer development if the young person is collaborating with others who are also within their ZPD (Bowler et al, 2005). Some research

in to ZPD has been performed to establish its relationship with BB. Hill et al (2020) found within their review of past research that young footballers being able to compete with peers of a similar maturity status should see them being challenged sufficiently in order to develop. However, they did suggest that mixed maturity could also benefit early maturing young footballers as they may view this as an opportunity to mentor and support less mature footballers, which could consolidate their learning and understanding of the game (Hill et al, 2020). The findings of Vygotsky's (1978) research also further strengthen the use of SSG's during football by suggesting that learning can only be identified through the active demonstration of the desired outcome (Jones et al, 2018). With the need for the young footballers to be performing within close to game like situations as possible, SSG's appear to be one of the best options in achieving this (Halouani et al, 2014). Research performed by Barrett et al (2022) examining the effect of BB in SSG's with youth footballers RPE, found there to be an increase in exertion levels when footballers competed with footballers of a similar maturity level. These findings could be deemed important to the present study as when viewed in conjunction with other past research it could suggest that by footballers competing within similar maturity levels could place them in to their ZPD, thus having a larger developmental impact upon individual footballers. However, Barret's et al (2022) research did not include any changes to SSG's format or relative pitch size, so further research would be required to determine any effect.

There have been a number of investigations into BB, SSG's and the impact they can have on footballers technically (Towlson et al, 2021) and physically (Barrett et al, 2022). However, no investigation has looked at their combined effects. The current research project will compare two groups of footballers of differing maturity status, within different functions of SSG. Firstly,

it will examine the impact of relative pitch size and game format on perceived exertion and physical load of youth footballers. Secondly, the current study will examine the impact of relative pitch size and game format on the technical performance of the youth footballers.

2.0 METHODS

2.1 Participants

Table 1. The table displays the numbers and characteristics of participants in relation to their maturity group.

TEAM	NUMBER OF FOOTBALLERS	CHRONOLOGICAL AGE (YEARS)	MATURITY OFFSET SCORE	STATURE (CM)	MASS (KG)	SEATED STATURE (CM)
OVERALL	48	13.38 ± 0.92	0.98 ± 1.01	162.06 ± 10.23	50.09 ± 10.23	79.54 ± 5.18
MORE A	12	13.96 ± 0.61	-0.08 ± 0.69	170.21 ± 6.79	58.23 ± 10.74	83.14 ± 4.26
MORE B	12	14.04 ± 0.40	-0.30 ± 0.81	168.82 ± 9.83	55.80 ± 8.05	82.88 ± 5.51
LESS A	12	12.43 ± 0.77	-2.02 ± 0.48	153.15 ± 6.17	42.50 ± 4.53	75.13 ± 2.62
LESS B	12	13.08 ± 0.74	-1.53 ± 0.35	156.07 ± 7.94	43.83 ± 5.77	77.00 ± 2.23

The research consisted of 48 young footballers (13.47 ± 0.85) from two separate Club Academy Scotland youth academies. The academies were visited on 3 consecutive weeks, on the same evening each week during regular training times. Week 1 was completed by 32 young footballers (4v4), with week 2 seeing an increase to 40 young footballers (5v5), with finally, week 3 used all 48 young footballers (6v6). The numbers and characteristics of the participants in relation to their maturity groups can be found in Table 1. The participating numbers were selected due to the need for SSG, while accommodating time and facility constraints. The young footballers were members of each academy's 2007, 2008, 2009 and 2010 born age groups. The young footballers selected to participate, competed amongst other members of their academies on a regular training night. The use of these participants is similar to those used within past research on BB (Ludin et al, 2021; Towlson et al, 2021). Ludin et al's (2021) study consisted of sixty-five adolescent footballers participating in Bio Banded (BB) and Chronological age (CA) SSG's over a period of two weeks. The footballers were part of a youth academies under-13 and under-14 squads and were categorised using by Maturity Offset scores (Ludin et al, 2021). Towlson et al (2021) had seventy-two adolescent footballers aged between eleven and fourteen from three different football academies, performing mis-matched and matched SSG's over a three-week period.

2.2 Experimental Design

For the present study the young footballers were categorised based upon their Biological Maturity status. Prior to the study, anthropometric data was collected by practitioners within each of the academies (Stature, Seated Stature and Mass) for each young footballer to allow for their Maturity Offset to be calculated. This process followed the standard procedures outlined by Lovell et al (2019) & Romann et al (2020) within their studies of a similar nature.

Maturity Offset scores were then used to split the young footballers based on if they were ‘less mature’ (-1.1/-2.5 years) or ‘more mature’ (+1/-1 years) than the median split of the group’s Age of Peak Height Velocity (APHV) scores as seen previously within Ludin et al (2021). Ludin et al (2021) believed this method to be especially accurate the closer the individuals are to their maturity offset, with the adolescent footballers within this current study believed to be very close to their maturity offset the use of this method should provide accurate data. However, in order to have enough participants to perform the study correctly the threshold had to be increased to -2.6, which may have negatively affected the accuracy of the data. Once the two maturity categories were filled with footballers, teams could be formed. The teams were formed without any knowledge of each footballer’s ability level which ensured no bias or mismatched teams. Prior to the beginning of the games on each visit, all young footballers completed the “FIFA 11” warm up (Bizzini et al, 2013) in an attempt to standardise the activity leading up to the games and to reduce the likelihood of injury during competitive match play. The first section of games saw four teams formed, More A, More B, Less A and Less B (The more teams were filled with footballers from the ‘More Mature’ category, with the Less teams filled with footballers from the ‘Less Mature’ category). Each team played three five-minute SSG in the first section, one maturity matched game and two Bio-Banded maturity games (see appendix 1). The second section of games saw four new teams created, Mixed A, Mixed B, Mixed C and Mixed D. These four teams were filled with footballers from both the ‘More Mature’ and ‘Less Mature’ Categories. It must be noted that during the 5v5 mixed games, some teams would have consisted of 3 MM + 2 LM, while other 2MM + 3LM, which was unavoidable due to the set-up of the research. Each team again played three five-minute SSG within this section; all games were mixed maturity games (see appendix 1) to provide a control where games were being played similarly to chronologically matched games. After the completion of each game, the young footballers taking part would verbally provide their RPE

score for the game to the researchers. The young footballers were asked to step away from their peers one at a time to provide their RPE. This was done to reduce the likelihood of the participants influencing each other's scores. In between the games, the teams not playing within the SSG, took part in a football tennis activity amongst their team in an attempt to standardise the activity between fixtures. Each week followed the same format but saw an increase in team size, while pitch size was adapted to be relative to the number of footballers on the pitch. Week one saw 4v4 on a relative pitch size of 40.3m x 28m, week two saw 5v5 on a relative pitch size of 44.1m x 32m and week three saw 6v6 on a relative pitch size of 47m x 36m. The relative pitch size for each pitch dimensions followed the area per footballer from a standard Scottish Football Association (SFA) 7v7 pitch (55m x 36m) (Scottish FA, 2022), this followed previous research in using area per footballer to create dimensions for SSG (Olthof et al, 2017). For example, within the present study the 4v4 relative pitch size was 40.3m x 28m, based on a total pitch area of 1,128m. When divided by the eight footballers returns the same area per footballer as the SFA 7v7 pitch (141m²).

2.3 Procedure

The current research project was provided ethics approval from the University of West of Scotland Ethics Committee (Ethics Number: 16783). Multiple Club Academy Scotland academies were invited to participate using the research team's existing professional contacts, with two expressing interest and being selected. Each footballer (see appendix 2) and parent/guardian (appendix 3) were provided an Information Sheet, containing all details of the study and their involvement within it. An online consent form (Microsoft Forms) was then completed for each footballer by themselves and their parent or guardian (see appendix 4), thus allowing the young footballers to participate through informed consent. The present study was carried out on regular training nights over three consecutive weeks and were held in the club's

academy facilities to ensure the footballers were completing similar activities to a regular training night. This set up follows that of similar existing research, such as Towlson et al (2021). Within Towlson et al's (2021) study they investigated the effect of BB on physical and psychological characteristics. The study included adolescent footballers performing SSG's over three sessions during their usual academy training, over a three-week period. During the sessions, the researchers collected internal and external load data from each footballer. Within the present research the internal load of each footballer was collected through the use of RPE. RPE from each SSG were collected verbally. The footballers were shown a RPE Borg Scale showing the numbers 1-10. 1 being very light with 10 being maximum effort (see appendix 5). The footballers were familiar with the scale having it explained to them prior to the beginning of each session. RPE was used due to the recommendation of Haddad et al (2017), who having examined over 36 studies that used the CR-10 RPE Scale found that it provides a well-rounded scoring system provided by the footballers themselves. External loads were collected through the use of PlayerMaker units. The PlayerMaker system provides a number of physical metrics, however, the most commonly reported metrics shown through existing literature will be used within this study (Sobolewski, 2020) to determine football performance. The physical metrics used in the final analysis were Total Distance (m), Total high-intensity distance (m) and total number of intense speed changes (#).

2.4 Inertial Measurement Units

During the SSG, data was collected through the use of the foot mounted PlayerMaker (London, United Kingdom) units, which are a brand of inertial measurement units. The PlayerMaker system calculates whole-body velocity-based metrics using data generated by the on-board MEMS, which uses a combination of proprietary gait tracking algorithm, permits detection of

the orientation and translation of the participants' limbs during gait cycles, while the event detection algorithm identifies key events during gait (heel strike, toe-off, zero-velocity, zero height, non-gait pattern) (Waldron et al, 2020). The microprocessor receives accelerometer and gyroscope data, from which orientation, velocity and position vectors are determined utilizing a Kalman Filter together with gait events update (Waldron et al, 2020). The resulting output provides a number of metrics related to football performance (Waldron et al, 2020). For the present study the technical football-based metrics used in the final analysis were Touches, Time on the Ball, High Intensity Releases and Number of Possessions. The physical metrics collected were total distance, high-intensity distance, and number of intense speed changes. These metrics were selected due to them being highlighted through literature as being important to successful football performance (Towlson et al 2021; Towlson et al 2021; Rhodes et al 2021). PlayerMaker units have been found to be reliable in their use during research (Waldron et al, 2020). When Waldron et al (2021) compared two PlayerMaker units, they found there to be no significant between the units' outputs (>0.05). However, to ensure reliability each footballer wore the same two units throughout each visit for the duration of the study.

2.5 Biological Maturity

The participants in the present study were categorised based upon their Maturity Offset scores. Data was collected prior to the beginning of the study in order to estimate each footballer's biological maturity, determine their Age at Peak Height Velocity (APHV) and calculate their Maturity Offset score (Towlson et al, 2021). The data collected was, date of birth, stature (cm), body mass (kg), and seated stature (cm). Maturity offset scores were then calculated using the Fransen Equation (Fransen et al, 2017) to provide each footballer with their APHV. A potential method that could have also provided the maturity offset data would have been the traditional method of assessing skeletal age through X-ray (Fransen et al, 2017). However, with the exposure to radiation as well as the costs related made it unusable within this study. Topor et al (2010) championed the use the Khamis-Roche method which they found to be effective in their research into the biological maturity of adolescents. However, this method requires physical data from both biological parents in order to be carried out which was deemed unsuitable, and logistically difficult, for the participants within this study. The Fransen Equation was deemed the most appropriate method to calculate the footballer's maturity offset scores due to it being found to be effective in its use with males in athletic settings, as well as it being the most time-friendly and least invasive method (Fransen et al, 2017). The young footballer's Biological Age is then subtracted from the APHV to give their Maturity Offset score. This method was used due to its use in previous similar studies that found it accurate in categorising adolescent male footballers (Ludin et al 2021; Towlson et al 2021). Due to the Maturity offset scores collected for the young footballers it was deemed appropriate to use 'more mature' or 'less mature' in order to categorise them. The 'More Mature' category consisted of young footballers whose maturity offset scores fell within +1.0 years to -1.0 years, while the 'Less Mature' category consisted of young footballers who's offset scores fell within -1.1 years to -2.6 years. These categories were created due to past research showing the further

an individual's score is from their APHV, the less accurate it is likely to be, with over 2.6 years having been deemed to have been too far to be accurate (Towlson et al, 2021), within this research footballers with a APHV score of over 2.6 were excluded.

2.6 Technical

Technical metrics were collected to analyse the young footballer's technical performance during SSG. The technical metrics were collected through the use of PlayerMaker units. The use of PlayerMaker was similar to work by Towlson et al (2021) who successfully used it to collect technical metrics of adolescent footballers. The PlayerMaker system provides the user with a number of technical metrics and certain metrics were selected due to their use in previous research (Kelly et al, 2020; Lewis et al, 2022). The technical metrics analysed were, Touches (#), Time on the Ball (#), Releases (#) and High Intensity Releases (#). Within Kelly et al's (2020) study that examined the technical attributes that are most commonly used within a talent identification setting to attempt to predict the potential future capabilities of adolescent footballers. Within their study, they analysed 98 footballers between the age of 9 and 11 performing a mix of technical tests and collecting data within match play and concluded that touches and time on the ball were the most important in determining the likelihood of selection. Lewis et al (2022) investigated adult footballers over a 25-week period, investigating the most important technical attributes to influence individual performance. Their results showed a high dependence on number of releases and number of high intensity releases for success during match-play.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Statistical Analysis was performed using the software Jamovi (2023). Descriptive statistics were calculated for the data set, then an ANOVA was used to statistically analyse each of the collected data points (technical & physical) within the context of each of the variables within this study; maturity levels, game format and pitch size used. Within the ANOVA, 'P values' were found for each of the data points which allowed the researcher to view if there were any significant differences in the technical and physical outputs depending on the game format, relative pitch size and maturity group. Firstly, standard descriptives were used, such as Mean, Median and SD for each of the data points in context to each variable, which allowed the researcher to gain context into the statistical differences. Once it had been shown that significant differences did exist within the collected data as a whole, post-hoc tests were carried out using 'Tukey' to provide comparisons for each data point in context to each variable, to allow the researcher to determine where these statistical differences were occurring within the data. Finally, standard descriptives were used, such as Mean, Median and SD for each of the data points in context to each variable, which allowed the researcher to gain context into the statistical differences. Within the results section, the results of technical metrics Total touches and Releases, and the results of the physical metrics Intense Speed Changes and RPE Load, were all rounded up to the nearest whole number to reflect the nature of their action. For example, to suggest that a footballer had 2.41 releases within a game, on average, does not intuitively make sense.

3.0 RESULTS

Table 2. The table displays the technical results of each maturity group, for each Relative Pitch Size and each Game Format.
More Mature

TECHNICAL METRIC	MISMATCHED			MIXED			MATCHED		
	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6
TOTAL TOUCHES (#)	20 ± 8	19 ± 9	20 ± 7	22 ± 8	21 ± 6	17 ± 6	25 ± 12	19 ± 5	19 ± 9
RELEASES (#)	8 ± 4	7 ± 3	8 ± 3	8 ± 3	7 ± 2	6 ± 2	10 ± 5	7 ± 3	8 ± 3
LONG POSSESSION (s)	3.38 ± 1.86	3.23 ± 2.29	3.46 ± 2.06	3.79 ± 1.88	3.68 ± 1.68	2.78 ± 1.58	3.81 ± 2.46	3.38 ± 1.86	3.79 ± 1.88
TOTAL TIME ON BALL (s)	12.25 ± 6.15	12.43 ± 8.88	12.42 ± 5.85	14.44 ± 7.98	14.02 ± 6.57	10.25 ± 6.16	14.75 ± 9.43	12.15 ± 5.93	11.71 ± 7.38

Less Mature

TECHNICAL METRIC	MISMATCHED			MIXED			MATCHED		
	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6
TOTAL TOUCHES (#)	20 ± 8	19 ± 9	13 ± 8	22 ± 11	17 ± 7	15 ± 7	23 ± 14	22 ± 8	16 ± 9
RELEASES (#)	8 ± 6	7 ± 4	5 ± 3	7 ± 4	6 ± 3	5 ± 3	8 ± 6	8 ± 3	5 ± 3
LONG POSSESSION	4.25 ± 3.41	2.83 ± 2.48	2.10 ± 1.57	3.90 ± 2.55	2.95 ± 1.94	2.59 ± 1.69	4.31 ± 3.26	3.75 ± 2.49	2.67 ± 1.93
TOTAL TIME ON BALL (s)	14.97 ± 11.07	11.15 ± 8.53	7.63 ± 5.95	13.77 ± 8.75	10.65 ± 6.39	9.41 ± 6.45	14.13 ± 11.63	12.75 ± 7.15	9.50 ± 6.11

Table 3. The table displays the physical results of each maturity group, for each Relative Pitch Size and each Game format.

More Mature

PHYSICAL METRIC	MISMATCHED			MIXED			MATCHED		
	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6
HID COVERED (m)	63.97 ± 35.11	64.15 ± 35.42	43.31 ± 32.81	67.27 ± 42.71	60.45 ± 35.56	54.07 ± 34.29	71.88 ± 35.83	64.30 ± 31.21	34.29 ± 22.64
DISTANCE COVERED (m)	568.41 ± 101.70	571.30 ± 71.04	542.44 ± 77.95	569.02 ± 65.13	552.47 ± 64.83	529.79 ± 69.92	694.88 ± 46.59	587.50 ± 65.63	513.17 ± 79.13
INTENSE SPEED	5 ± 3	5 ± 2	4 ± 3	14 ± 9	11 ± 6	9 ± 6	5 ± 3	6 ± 3	3 ± 2
RPE LOAD (#)	24 ± 5	23 ± 5	26 ± 7	22 ± 6	22 ± 7	24 ± 7	18 ± 4	18 ± 4	22 ± 5

Less Mature

PHYSICAL METRIC	MISMATCHED			MIXED			MATCHED		
	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6	4V4	5V5	6V6
HID COVERED (m)	86.66 ± 32.79	80.22 ± 32.43	65.52 ± 31.33	81.67 ± 36.37	75.25 ± 30.92	68.99 ± 38.30	78.69 ± 23.54	80.55 ± 40.44	50.50 ± 29.71
DISTANCE COVERED (m)	567.97 ± 48.68	563.95 ± 57.80	537.71 ± 62.28	551.54 ± 55.27	562.57 ± 59.86	525.99 ± 98.14	603.19 ± 55.28	585.45 ± 55.44	552.38 ± 63.30
INTENSE SPEED	7 ± 4	7 ± 3	6 ± 3	6 ± 3	14 ± 7	10 ± 6	6 ± 4	6 ± 3	5 ± 2
RPE LOAD (#)	16 ± 4	18 ± 5	19 ± 4	22 ± 7	21 ± 6	22 ± 6	21 ± 5	18 ± 4	21 ± 5

3.1 Maturity Groups

The two maturity groups, Maturity Offsets were compared using an independent sample T-test, this showed a statistical difference between the two groups maturity offset (MM = -0.56 ± 0.68 , LM = -1.57 ± 0.61 , P value = <0.001). The significant differences found from the changes in game format and team and pitch size showed the MM footballers (Stature = 169.0 ± 7.5 cm, Body Mass = 53.6 ± 8.9 kg, Maturity offset = -0.3 ± 0.6) performing a greater amount of the metric than the LM footballers (Stature = 152.8 ± 7.3 cm, Body Mass = 42.0 ± 5.7 kg, Maturity Offset = -1.7 ± 0.6). The only effect that saw the LM group perform more than the MM group was within the Mixed 6v6 game which saw them perform a significantly greater total distance.

3.2 Team & Pitch Size

The data has showed that the youth footballers physical load and technical actions appear to be affected due to adaptations to the team and pitch size. In particular the increase to 6v6 on a relative pitch size having a significant impact on three of the four technical action metrics. The increase of pitch size saw the MM footballers perform significantly more releases in mismatched (P= <0.001 , MM = 8 ± 3 , LM = 5 ± 3), in Mixed (P=0.019, MM = 6 ± 2 , LM = 5 ± 3) and in Matched (P=0.020, MM = 8 ± 3 , LM = 5 ± 3). Significantly more Total Touches in Mismatched (P=0.007, MM = 20 ± 7 , LM = 13 ± 8) and in Mixed (P=0.039, MM = 17 ± 6 , LM = 15 ± 7). And significantly more Long Possessions in Mismatched (P=0.031, MM = 3.46 ± 2.06 , LM = 2.10 ± 1.57) than LM footballers. There was no other significant effect on the technical actions on either group from relative pitch size, except from in 5v5, which saw MM footballers perform significantly more releases in Mixed games than LM footballers 5v5 (P=0.014, MM = 7 ± 2 , LM = 6 ± 3).

It appears that team and pitch size have similar effects on the physical load of both maturity groups. As was the case with technical actions there appeared to be no differences in any of the physical metrics between the LM and MM footballers within the 4v4 and 5v5 team and pitch size. However, as with the technical metrics there were effects found within the 6v6 team and pitch size. The two metrics that were affected were the total distance covered and total high intensity distance covered. In the 6v6 mismatched ($P= 0.041$, $MM = 65.52 \pm 31.33$, $LM = 43.31 \pm 32.81$) and matched ($P=0.006$, $MM = 50.50 \pm 29.71$, $LM = 34.29 \pm 22.64$) games, the MM footballers covered a significantly greater total high intensity distance than LM footballers. The effects on total distance appeared to also be influenced by the game type as within the Mixed game format ($P= 0.013$, $MM = 525.99 \pm 98.14$, $LM = 529.79 \pm 69.92$) the LM footballers covered a significantly greater total distance than MM footballers, however within the Matched ($P= 0.006$, $MM = 552.38 \pm 63.30$, $LM = 513.17 \pm 79.13$) game type the MM footballers covered a greater total distance than LM footballers.

There appeared to be no difference on the total time on the ball metric between the maturity groups in any of the team and pitch sizes. While the team and pitch size also showed no differences in the physical metrics, intense speed changes and RPE Load, of the maturity groups.

3.3 Game Format

Within the Mismatched game format there appeared to be some effect on both the technical and physical metrics. In terms of technical metrics, the mismatched games saw the MM footballers perform a significantly greater number of total touches ($P=0.007$, $MM = 20 \pm 7$, $LM = 13 \pm 8$) releases ($P= <0.001$, $MM = 8 \pm 3$, $LM = 5 \pm 3$) and long possessions ($P=0.031$, $MM = 3.46 \pm 2.06$, $LM = 2.10 \pm 1.57$) than LM footballers. The mismatched games appeared to affect the physical loads of the two groups as the MM footballers covered significantly

greater high intensity distance ($P= 0.041$, $MM = 65.52 \pm 31.33$, $LM = 43.31 \pm 32.81$) than LM footballers. All of the effects in Mismatched games occurred within the 6v6 team and relative pitch size.

The Mixed game format also saw effects in both the technical and physical metrics. It saw the MM footballers perform a significantly greater number of releases than LM footballers in both the 5v5 ($P= 0.014$, $MM = 7 \pm 2$, $LM = 6 \pm 3$) and 6v6 ($P=0.019$, $MM = 6 \pm 2$, $LM = 5 \pm 3$) team and relative pitch sizes. Furthermore, in the 6v6 mixed game saw the MM footballers achieve a significantly greater number of total touches ($P=0.039$, $MM = 17 \pm 6$, $LM = 15 \pm 7$)

The Matched game format again showed an effect on both technical and physical metrics and again only showed them within the 6v6 team and relative pitch size. Within the technical metrics it was shown that the MM footballers performed a significantly greater number of releases ($P=0.020$, $MM = 8 \pm 3$, $LM = 5 \pm 3$) than LM footballers. While the matched game format effected the physical load, as the MM footballers performed a significantly greater total distance ($P= 0.006$, $MM = 552.38 \pm 63.30$, $LM = 513.17 \pm 79.13$) and total high intensity distance ($P=0.009$, $MM = 50.50 \pm 29.71$, $LM 34.29 \pm 22.64$) than LM footballers.

In all 3 of the differing game formats there appeared to be no effect on the total time on the ball, with the technical metric showing no difference between the two maturity groups in any of the team and relative pitch sizes. While the Intense speed changes and RPE load of both groups also were not affected by the differing game formats again in any of the team and relative pitch sizes.

4.0 DISCUSSION

The present study examined the effects that different pitch size and game formats had on the technical actions and physical load of adolescent footballers of differing maturity levels. The results showed that increases in team and pitch size appeared to provide the opportunity for MM to use their increased physical capabilities to perform greater physical and technical actions than LM. Furthermore, it may be appropriate for coaches to consider BB game formats in order to ensure that LM are exposed to the same physical demands as MM during SSG. Within the results significant differences in the number of technical actions performed by the LM and MM footballers within the different team size and game formats were evident. However, clear effects appeared to be related to the changes in relative pitch size. The findings showed that as the teams were increased to 6v6 on a relative pitch size, the difference in technical actions between LM and MM seemed to increase in favour of the MM footballers. These findings were demonstrated in all three of the game formats (Mismatched, Mixed and Matched), which may suggest they are greater related to the pitch and team size than the game format. Previous research of a similar type would agree with the findings in the present study (Clemente et al 2021). Within their systematic review of 50 studies examining SSG's in football they concluded that adapting the pitch and team size of the games could elicit effects on the footballer's technical outputs. Further existing research from Aguiar et al (2012) suggests the same as they found that their team and relative pitch size adaptations were having an effect on the youth footballers' technical actions. However, although it is clear that the increase to the 6v6 team size as a relative pitch size was affecting the technical actions of the youth footballers in the present study, the significant difference between MM and LM showed that it was having differing effects depending on maturity status. The MM footballers were shown to be performing significantly more technical actions within the 6v6 team size games than the LM

(to various extents depending on game format), when in the previous 4v4 and 5v5 team sizes there had been no significant differences found. One reason for the differing technical data recorded by the two groups could be related to their differing maturity status. A study that would be useful to compare this studies' results to would be Lovell et al's (2019). Within Lovell et al's (2019) study they had youth footballers (15 ± 0.4 -year-old) competing in BB games over a 3-day period, similar to the set-up of the present study. The footballers were also split into maturity levels using their APHV and the Fransen maturity ratio. However, something that should be noted is that the youth footballers were competing within full 11v11 games, not SSG like those used in the present study. Lovell et al's (2019) findings could suggest that the reason for the difference in technical actions is due to the MM footballers being capable of covering a greater distance at greater speeds than the LM footballers, which could give them an advantage over LM footballers as the pitch and team size increases. This would appear to mirror the results of the current study as it shows there are no significant difference between the two groups technical actions within the 4v4 team size games, and only a single metric (releases (#)) showing a significant difference between the two groups in the 5v5 game in the three different game formats. These findings seem to suggest that a smaller pitch and team size may be able to remove or reduce the effects caused by variation in maturity status. The results in the present study seem to suggest that the bigger 6v6 team and relative pitch size allows the MM footballers to use their advanced physical ability to perform to a greater level than LM both physically and technically. In the 4v4 and 5v5 team and relative pitch size the MM footballers are unable to use their advanced physical capabilities on the larger the relative pitch size (6v6) to create and advantage physically and technically over the LM footballers. Thus, allowing the LM footballers the opportunity to perform physical and technical metrics to the same level as MM footballers.

A further way in which it appears the effect of differing maturity levels can be reduced is through the 'Matched' BB game format. It can be seen from the results of the present study that the 'Matched' game format does show a smaller number of significant differences regarding technical actions between the two groups when compared with the two other game formats during the 6v6 team size ('Mismatched' and 'Mixed'). This may suggest that although the team and relative pitch size are having a differing effect on the technical actions of the two groups as they increase to 6v6, by using BB style 'Matched' games, it could reduce these effects.

The findings of 'Matched' game potentially reducing effects of differing maturity levels on technical actions could have an effect when considering the youth footballers ZPD (Zone of Proximal Development) (Vygotsky, 1978). The ZPD is described as the distance between the actual development level of an adolescent as determined by their independent problem-solving and the level of their potential development as determined through their ability to problem solve while under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers (Vygotsky, 1978, P.86). Vinson & Parker (2019) found the likelihood of an adolescent to be performing within their ZPD to be increased if they are performing with peers within a similar level to them. When relating this to the findings of the present study it would suggest that the most likely situation for the footballers of both maturity groups to be performing within their ZPD would be the 4v4 team size, due to their being no differences found in their technical or physical metrics. In terms of the 6v6, where teams' size showed significant differences between the two maturity groups in certain technical and physical metrics, this would appear to be in line with the literature of Hill et al (2020). The researchers stated that they believed there to be a relationship between ZPD and BB within youth footballers, with the increased likelihood of them being in their ZPD when competing with footballers of a similar maturity level. The findings of the present study support this in terms of technical development as there were fewer differences between MM and LM footballers when they were competing within the 'matched'

game format within the 6v6 team size, unlike the ‘mismatched’ and ‘mixed’ which saw significant differences. This suggests that BB could be appropriate for keeping footballers competing within their ZPD in terms of technical actions, even when the pitch and team size is favouring MM footballers.

The technical metric ‘Total time on the ball’ did not show any significant differences between the two maturity groups within any of the team sizes and any of the game formats. However, Kelly et al (2020) had previously dismissed its use as a metric within their study to successfully analyse youth footballers within SSG’s. Throughout a full season the research studied 98 outfield youth academy footballers in England. During the SSG’s the researchers used 8 different analysis statistics to study youth footballer’s technical skills behaviour. They deemed time on the ball to not be within the top eight technical metrics to analyse youth footballers within SSG’s, to access the talent development process within English football academies. This present study’s findings would appear to align as it suggested that the use of time on the ball is not a useful technical statistic to analyse youth footballers of differing biological maturity.

The results of the present study showed significant differences between the two maturity groups physical load when performing the SSG’s regarding the different game formats and team sizes. The findings regarding physical load appeared to echo those of the technical actions, in that differences seemed to be most pronounced during 6v6 team size games regardless of game format used. The results showed that there were no significant differences between the physical loads of LM footballers and MM footballers when playing in a 4v4 or 5v5 team size in a relative pitch, in any of the three game formats used (‘Mismatched’, ‘Matched’, or ‘Mixed’). The metrics analysed (High intensity distance covered, Distance Covered, Intense Speed Changes & RPE Load) were chosen due to them being shown in previous research to be the most

appropriate in capturing a footballer's level of physical load during a game of football (Haddad et al 2017) However, it must be noted that the youth footballers used within Haddad et al (2017), were of older age (17.6 ± 0.7) than the footballers in this study (13.47 ± 0.85). In relation to existing research, the findings of this present study showed that there was no difference between the physical metrics would suggest that the 4v4 and 5v5 team size SSG's on a relative pitch size allow for LM and MM footballers to compete together without positively or negatively effecting either of the group's physical performance, regardless of the game format used. The game formats could be used to reduce the impact of the MM footballers increased physical prowess which allows them to dominate over LM in larger sized game formats (Bradley et al, 2022). Previous research that may explain why these findings differ from what has been previously reported about BB can be viewed in the studies of both Romann et al (2020) and Abbott et al (2019). Romann et al's (2020) research consisted of 33 youth footballers (Age 12.2 ± 0.3 years) split into 'Less Mature' and 'More Mature' groups based upon their APHV, similar to this study. However, they used 11v11 full sided games as opposed to SSG, as they found SSG to reduce the physical demands of youth footballers. Furthermore, within Abbott et al's (2019) research, which consisted of 25 youth footballers (Age 12.7 ± 1.0 years), being split in to 'Less Mature' and 'More Mature' groups and similarly to Romann et al (2020) competed in full sided 11v11 games as again it was deemed the SSG would reduce the physical demands of the youth footballers to be used.

The 6v6 team sized games showed differences between the two groups in their total distance covered and their high intensity distance covered, with the MM covering a significantly greater high intensity distance in the 'Matched' and 'Mismatched' 6v6 games, while also performing a significantly greater total distance in the 'Matched' 6v6. However, it was found that LM performed a significantly greater total distance than MM in the 'Mixed' 6v6. These findings,

when compared with the findings from Lovell et al (2019) who found that maturity levels of MM footballers could be seen to significantly affect the physical performance of the footballers during games. Showing that MM footballers were able to run faster and further than LM footballers. These results could explain why there is a significant difference between the two-maturity group's total distance covered, and high intensity distance covered in some of the different team and relative pitch size and Game formats used. Within the 6v6 'Mismatched' and 'Matched' maturity games, the findings show that they support the previous research as they both show MM footballers performed a greater high intensity distance, while 'Matched' also shows that they performed a significantly greater Total Distance. However, within the Mixed Maturity group games, the results disagree with the previous research as they show the LM footballers to have covered a significantly greater distance than the MM footballers.

Furthermore, these findings could be again related back to research of both Romann et al (2020) and Abbott et al (2019), with both studies showing that the use of SSG's had been found to reduce the physical demands placed on youth footballers during SSG's. In this present studies case, it may appear that the team and relative pitch size of the SSG's had reduced the physical demands to a certain extent, thus not allowing for the maturity status of the youth footballers completely effect the physical results.

In terms of the difference of two maturity groups physical loads effect on their ZPD, it appeared to echo that of the technical actions, in suggesting that 4v4 and 5v5 team sizes would allow for the greatest number of footballers to be competing within their ZPD in regard to their technical actions. This suggestion again is based upon the previous findings of Vinson & Parker (2019) stated that and adolescents' ability to perform within the ZPD was aided by performing with peers of a similar level. Due to the findings for 4v4 and 5v5 teams showing no significant difference it would show that the footballers were performing at a similar level of physical load which would aid upon them performing in their ZPD. This would benefit the youth footballers

as the principals of ZPD show it is crucial that they are tested enough to allow them to improve, but not tested too much that they are unable to improve (Vinson & Parker, 2019). With the aim of youth academies to continually improve the youth footballers towards senior football, this would align clearly with their aims.

Two of the physical metrics used to quantify the physical load of the two maturity groups showed no significant difference for either group, in any of the team sizes, in any of the game formats. Intense Speed Changes and RPE Load appeared to not be affected by the changes in team size and relative pitch size or by the differing maturity-based games formats. Intense Speed changes was selected due to the findings of Sobolewski (2020) who believed it to be one of the most important physical factors in analysing physical load in football. However, within this present study it appears it's not affected by the differing maturity levels of the two groups. RPE was selected due to Haddad et al (2017), who examined the validity and reliability of RPE measures in over 36 different studies including several different sporting activities, with athletes of varying age and genders. Their results showed it to be reliable and consistent, however they did admit that it does force young athletes to express their own personal feelings in performing it, which may have affected the outcomes when you relate it back to the age of the youth footballers involved within this present study. However, Sanchez et al (2017) used RPE with youth footballers in SSG and found them to be accurate. 22 youth footballers competed in six different SSG formats while having their Heart Rate, RPE and Technical Actions recorded, which is similar to the present study, as it was collecting physical and technical data from the youth footballers.

As the results suggest that the 4v4 team size has no differing effects on the physical or technical metrics of the two maturity groups within this present study, regardless of the maturity level

game format, it could be suggested that 4v4 games on a relative pitch size would be effective for allowing a group of different maturity footballers to compete without negatively effecting each other's development. With the previous research suggesting that performing with similarly levelled peers can support adolescents in performing within their ZPD (Vygotsky, 1978; Vinson & Parker, 2019), it could also be suggested that 4v4 team size would allow this as there were no significant differences in the physical or technical metrics found in the results of the two different maturity groups. 5v5 team sized games appear to follow the same effects as the 4v4 team size as they showed no effects when comparing the two groups physical load on all three game formats, and only showing a significant effect on the technical action 'Releases' during the 'Mixed' game format. It appears 5v5 could be used for a group of different maturity level footballers if the main aim of the SSG's was physical based, however, if it was focused upon technical development then it may be beneficial to use BB to ensure the two groups are not affecting each other. Finally, 6v6 game format has shown that it can affect the two maturity groups in both physical load and technical actions. If the aim of the SSG was to develop the physical capabilities of a group of footballers with different maturity levels, then it would appear a mix of BB and 'Mixed' would be required to ensure the mutual benefit for the full group. With BB ('Mismatched' and 'Matched') appearing to elicit a greater level of physical load for MM footballers than LM footballers, while a 'Mixed' 6v6 game could aid the LM footballers in improving their physical ability. This was shown in the research of Halouani et al (2014) who found in their review of SSG research from over the past 39 years, that there was clear evidence that a SSG that increased the physical demand of the footballers would in turn see positive physical adaptations in that footballer over time. If the aim is to target the technical actions of a group of young footballers of differing maturity levels through a 6v6 team sized SSG then it could be viewed as again being beneficial to use a mixture of 'Mixed' and 'Matched' BB game formats. 'Mixed' games appear to benefit the MM footballers more

than LM, while ‘Matched’ BB games appear to increase the physical and technical metrics to the MM footballers which will aid the development of MM.

5.0 PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings from this current study could be used by youth football coaches to adapt their use of SSG’s to maximise youth footballer’s development. A coach with a diverse group of players in terms of their maturity levels could use the findings, that the use of 4v4 SSG’s would allow all players to compete physically and technically to the same level. If the coach wanted to use a larger team and pitch size (e.g. 5v5, 6v6) they must be aware of the effects it will have on their group of footballers as it has been demonstrated that the MM footballers will perform a significantly greater number of physical and technical actions. To prevent this from negatively effecting the LM footballers of the group the coaches could use ‘Matched’ games as they have been shown to mitigate the impact that physicality can have on matchplay.

6.0 LIMITATIONS

The study has several strengths, with it being a real-world study set in an applied setting. The study followed the logistical process used within previous successful studies, such as Towlson et al (2021), by using youth footballers within their usual football academy setting, strengthening the ecological validity of the study. A further strength was the use of multiple game formats and multiple team and pitch sizes, which provided a broader insight in to how a number of different game formats and pitch sizes can influence both the physical and

technical demands of SSG in youth football. However, the study is not without limitations. In this current study the Fransen equation was used to assign the footballers into their maturity groups. This could be seen as limitation as it is believed that the Khamis-Roche Equation would have provided a greater level of accuracy to the footballer's maturity level. However, due to the nature of the participant groups used, the required information (parental stature) wouldn't have been available. A further limitation due to the use of the Fransen Equation was the requirement to extend the LM offset scores to -2.6, to ensure enough participants were available to fulfil team sizes. This could be a limitation as it is found that the further a maturity offset score is from the individual's APHV the less accurate it is believed to be (Towlson et al, 2021) .

7.0 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it would appear that game format and relative pitch size does have an effect on adolescent footballers of differing maturity levels within SSG. However, it has been shown that the effect can be different depending on the maturity level of each adolescent footballer, the game format, and the relative pitch size. Smaller relative pitch sizes appear to affect the two maturity groups to a lesser extent physically and technically which may allow for both groups to be tested equally. As the relative pitch size increases the effects appeared to provide the opportunity for MM to use their increased physical capabilities to perform greater physical and technical actions than LM. Game formats can have varying effects on the two differing maturity groups, such as 'Mismatched' and 'Mixed' games allowing the MM to perform a greater number of technical actions than LM, while 'Matched' games saw LM perform a greater number of physical actions than MM. However, it must be noted that the

effects of game formats were lessened by the reduction of relative pitch size. Therefore, it would be recommended that if coaching a group of adolescent footballers of varying maturity levels, then the use of a smaller pitch size would lessen the effect of the differing groups, physically and technically. In future it would be beneficial to compare the findings of this research in to SSG to the findings of the relative pitch sizes used in competitive adolescent football matches in the United Kingdom (7v7,9v9,11v11) to establish if the effects of maturity continue.

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Appendix 1

<i>TIMINGS</i>	<i>TEAM</i>	<i>ACTIVITY</i>	<i>TEAM</i>	<i>WEEK 1</i>	<i>WEEK 2</i>	<i>WEEK 3</i>
10 Minutes		Introduction				
10 Minutes		Warm Up (Fifa 11)				
1 Minutes		Set Up				
5 Minutes	Late A	vs	Late B	4V4 (40.3m x 28m)	5V5 (44.1m x 32m)	6V6 (47m x 36m)
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Early A	vs	Early B	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Late B	vs	Early A	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Early A	vs	Late A	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Late B	vs	Early B	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Late A	vs	Early B	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE				
5 Minutes		Break				
5 Minutes	Mixed A	vs	Mixed B	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Mixed C	vs	Mixed D	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Mixed B	vs	Mixed C	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Mixed C	vs	Mixed A	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Mixed B	vs	Mixed D	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE + Changes				
5 Minutes	Mixed A	vs	Mixed D	4v4	5V5	6V6
30 seconds		RPE				

Appendix 2

Participant Information Sheet - Child

Research Title:

“The influence of ‘team size’ on maturity status ‘bio-banding’ when using a multidisciplinary approach to identify talented adolescent soccer players”

Purpose of the study:

The main objective of this study will be to establish the effect of varying numbers of players per team (4 Vs. 4; 5 Vs. 5; 6 Vs. 6; 7 Vs. 7) during bio-banded, small-sided games on players’ tactical, technical, psychological and physical characteristics when relative pitch size is controlled for (i.e., on the same size of pitch, regardless of how many players are in the team). This can help coaches and performance staff make more informed decisions regarding how ‘bio-banding’ is implemented, together with providing them with a greater understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the method. Ultimately, this will encourage talent (de)selection practitioners to consider player maturity status during match analysis and player retention/development policies, and give them a greater insight into potential ‘hidden’ talents that some players may possess, that may not often appear when playing in chronological age groups.

Why have I been approached to take part?

You are currently signed as a player at a professional youth academy and participate in regular, football specific, training. Several Scottish Academies have been approached to participate in this study and your team have shown an interest in taking part.

Do I have to take part?

Participation in this study is entirely optional, if you do decide to take part you will be asked to complete a consent form. Even after you have decided to take part, you are able to withdraw at any time without giving a specified reason. Your participation or non-participation in this study will have no effect in anyway on your position within your team or academy. Simply, there will be no reward or punishment from your club based upon your decision to participate.

What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to attend your regular training facility and take part in a series of small-sided games where you will be categorised by your biological maturity status (the proximity to your biggest growth spurt as a teenager). This can be calculated by taking things like your height and weight into account, and can be collected by researchers, or coaches at your club. This data will be used to class players into separate bio-banded groups. In these groups, you will be paired with other players who are going through similar growth periods as you. As an example, another player in your bio-banded team may be slightly taller than you, but you will both be at roughly the same stage of biological maturity and be similar distance away from your biggest change in maturation. After completing 3 games in your bio-banded groups, you will then play another 3 games where the teams will be mixed. Each match will be 5 minutes in duration, and players will contest 6 matches (3 bio-banded; 3 mixed) each constituting 30 minutes total playing time per player per week (90 minutes in total). Coaches and representatives from your club will be present for each of the small-sided games.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

The investigator does not see any possible disadvantages of taking part, due to the study consisting of activities similar to those of a normal training session you would experience with your club.

The potential benefits of taking part:

The benefits of taking part in the study is that you will get play lots of small-sided games over a 3-week period where you will be playing with and against players from within your academy who you

Appendix 3

Participant Information Sheet - Parent/Guardian

Research Title:

“The influence of ‘team size’ on maturity status ‘bio-banding’ when using a multidisciplinary approach to identify talented adolescent soccer players”

Purpose of the study:

The main objective of this study will be to establish the effect of varying numbers of players per team (4 Vs. 4; 5 Vs. 5; 6 Vs. 6; 7 Vs. 7) during bio-banded, small-sided games on players’ tactical, technical, psychological and physical characteristics when relative pitch size is controlled for (i.e., same size of pitch, regardless of how many players are in the team). The current study will allow further examination of the effect of ‘bio-banding’ during games contested by teams comprised of various numbers of players and help practitioners, coaches and performance staff make more informed decisions regarding how ‘bio-banding’ is implemented, together with providing them with a greater understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the method. Ultimately, this will encourage talent (de)selection practitioners to consider player maturity status during match analysis and player retention/development policies, and give them a greater insight into potential ‘hidden’ talents that some players may possess, that may not often appear during chronological banding.

Why has my child been approached to take part?

Your child is currently signed as a player at a professional youth academy and participates in regular, football specific, training. Several Scottish Academies have been approached to participate in this study and your child’s team have shown an interest in taking part.

Does my child have to take part?

Parents will be requested to provide consent, and players requested for assent, to participate in the research study. All participants reserve the right to withdraw from the study at any point should they feel necessary without having to provide a specified reason. Should your child decide to take part in the study a consent form will need to be completed by both the parent/guardian and the child. Your child’s participation or non-participation in this study will have no effect in anyway on their position within your team or academy. Simply, there will be no reward or punishment from your child’s club based upon their decision to participate.

What will happen to my child if they take part?

They will be asked to attend their regular training facility and take part in a series of small-sided games where they will be categorised by biological maturity status (the proximity to your child’s biggest growth spurt as a teenager).

Maturity status can be calculated by measuring their height, seated height and weight, and can be (collected by researchers). This data will be used to class players into separate bio-banded groups. In these groups, your child will be paired with other players who are going through similar growth periods as them.

Each match will be 5 minutes in duration, and players will contest 6 matches (3 bio-banded; 3 mixed) each constituting 30 minutes total playing time per player per week (90 minutes in total).

Appendix 4

Consent Form

I....., agree to participate in the research project titled *“The influence of ‘team size’ on maturity status ‘bio-banding’ when using a multidisciplinary approach to identify talented adolescent soccer players”*.

Pupil:

- The purpose and nature of the study has been explained to me in writing.
- I am participating voluntarily.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time, whether before it starts or while I am participating.
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions regarding the study and all the questions that I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction.

Parent/Guardian:

- I agree that my child’s participation is completely voluntarily, they provide assent prior to participation, and should they decide to withdraw from the study, either before or during, there will be no repercussions regarding their standing within the academy.
 - I agree that the purpose and nature of this study has been explained to me in writing.
 - I agree that I have had the opportunity to ask questions regarding the study and that any questions I have asked, have been answered in a satisfactory manner.
 - I agree to the collection of anthropometric data (i.e., height, seated height and weight) from my child, in order to determine their maturity status for grouping.
 - I understand that the physical, technical, tactical and psychological performance of my child will be examined during each of the small-sided matches, and I agree to the collection of this data.
-

Appendix 5

RATE OF PERCEIVED EXERTION

10	MAXIMAL
9	
8	
7	VERY HARD
6	
5	HARD
4	SOMEWHAT HARD
3	MODERATE
2	EASY
1	VERY VERY EASY
0	REST